

STRAIGHTEDGE AND COMPASS CONSTRUCTIONS OF LINE SEGMENTS APPROXIMATING π

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ABSTRACT. This paper presents a series of novel and elegant geometric constructions using a straightedge and compass to produce line segments whose lengths are very close to the number π . To rigorously evaluate the intrinsic quality and simplicity of the underlying approximations, we employ the concept of the “measure of intelligence”.

1. INTRODUCTION

The number π has fascinated mathematicians since ancient times, giving rise to one of the most famous and enduring geometric challenges in the history of mathematics: squaring the circle. This age-old problem involves determining whether it is possible to construct a square whose area is exactly equal to that of a given circle, using only a finite number of steps with a compass and a straightedge. Algebraically, this amounts to constructing a line segment of length $\sqrt{\pi}$, which is also equivalent to constructing a line segment of length π . Despite the relentless efforts of Greek mathematicians (such as Anaxagoras, Hippocrates of Chios, and Archimedes) and later Islamic mathematicians (such as Ibn al-Haytham and Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Tūsī), the exact squaring of the circle resisted all attempts.

In 1837, Wantzel [7] discovered the algebraic characterization of numbers constructible with a straightedge and compass. Broadly speaking, his theorem states that a real number is constructible with a straightedge and compass if and only if it can be expressed (in a finite number of steps) using only the four fundamental arithmetic operations ($+$, $-$, \times , \div) and the extraction of square roots ($\sqrt{\quad}$). It follows from this theorem that a number constructible by straightedge and compass is necessarily algebraic (that is, it is a root of a non-zero polynomial with integer coefficients). A few decades later, in 1882, Lindemann [5] brilliantly demonstrated that π is a transcendental number (i.e., non-algebraic), thereby definitively establishing the impossibility of squaring the circle.

Faced with this absolute impossibility, the quest for approximations of π that are both highly accurate and geometrically constructible becomes a unique, natural, and historically rich alternative. Over the centuries, mathematicians have proposed various rational and algebraic approximations. Examples include Archimedes’ famous approximation $\pi \approx \frac{22}{7}$ and the remarkably precise fraction established by the Chinese astronomer Zu Chongzhi, $\pi \approx \frac{355}{113}$ (see e.g., [1]). As for non-rational approximations that

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Date: March 21, 2026.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification. Primary 51M15; Secondary 11J04.

Key words and phrases. Approximation of π , Geometric constructions, Straightedge and compass, Squaring the circle, Measure of intelligence.

can be constructed using a straightedge and compass, perhaps the most famous example is Kochański's approximation $\pi \approx \sqrt{\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}}$ (see [4]). However, a fundamental epistemological question arises: how can one quantitatively assess the elegance, simplicity, or intrinsic “quality” of such an approximation? To answer this rigorously, the author introduced in [2] the concept of the *measure of intelligence* (or relevance measure) of an approximation of a real number within a given model. Building on the notion of the complexity of a number—defined by the number of its digits in a given base—this mathematical framework introduces a function μ that assigns a positive real number to every approximation, thereby effectively measuring its quality. More precisely, an approximation is considered “intelligent” if and only if its measure satisfies $\mu \geq 1$.

In order to make this paper self-contained and to allow the reader to easily evaluate the approximations presented herein, let us formally recall this concept:

Definition 1.1 ([2]). Let n be a positive integer, let $f : \mathbb{Z}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function, and let α be a non-zero real number. Suppose that

$$\alpha \approx f(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \quad (*)$$

is an approximation of α , where $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{Z}^*$ such that $a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n \neq \pm 1$. The *measure of intelligence* of $(*)$, denoted by $\mu(*)$, is defined as:

$$\mu(*) := \frac{\log |\alpha| - \log |\alpha - f(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)|}{\log |a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n|}.$$

We say that the approximation $(*)$ is *intelligent* if $\mu(*) \geq 1$, and *naive* otherwise.

Note that the larger the measure of intelligence, the more intelligent the approximation is considered to be. We refer the reader to [2] for the detailed rationale behind this conceptual framework.

The aim of this paper is to present a series of novel and elegant geometric constructions using a (graduated) straightedge and compass to produce line segments whose lengths approximate the number π with a high degree of accuracy and a good measure of intelligence. We conclude the article by providing a few approximations of π that are entirely constructible using a straightedge and compass, but for which finding an explicit and elegant geometric construction remains a stimulating challenge. Unless otherwise stated, both the numerical approximations and their corresponding geometric constructions introduced herein are due to the author.

2. THE CONSTRUCTIONS

Construction 1. This construction relies on the famous rational approximation of Archimedes:

$$\pi \approx \frac{22}{7}, \quad (1)$$

which has an error of $\approx 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$ and a measure of intelligence of ≈ 1.55 . We proceed as follows:

Construct a right trapezoid $ABCD$ with base BC , such that $AB = 3$, $BC = 7$, and $CD = 2$. Next, construct the perpendicular bisector (Δ) of the segment AD . This line intersects the base BC of the trapezoid at a point H . We then obtain:

$$BH = \frac{22}{7} \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. Let us set $x = BH$ and compute AH^2 and DH^2 in terms of x . Applying the Pythagorean theorem to the right triangles ABH and DCH , we respectively obtain:

$$AH^2 = BH^2 + AB^2 = x^2 + 3^2 = x^2 + 9,$$

and

$$DH^2 = CH^2 + CD^2 = (BC - BH)^2 + CD^2 = (7 - x)^2 + 2^2 = x^2 - 14x + 53.$$

However, since the point H lies on the perpendicular bisector of the segment AD , we have $AH = DH$, which implies $AH^2 = DH^2$. This yields the following equation in terms of x :

$$x^2 + 9 = x^2 - 14x + 53.$$

The unique solution to this equation (which readily simplifies to a linear equation) is $x = \frac{22}{7}$. Hence, $BH = \frac{22}{7}$, as required. \square

Construction 2. We utilize the approximation:

$$\pi \approx 3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1}, \quad (2)$$

which was previously reported in our article [2], where we also indicated a simple method to derive it from the regular continued fraction expansion of the number π .

Let us briefly recall this method. Using the standard notation for regular continued fractions (see, e.g., [3]), we have:

$$\pi = [3; 7, 15, 1, 292, 1, \dots] \approx [3; 7, 15, 1] = [3; 7, 16] \approx [3; 7, \overline{16}] = 3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1}.$$

The approximation (2) yields an error of $\approx 5.1 \times 10^{-6}$ and has a measure of intelligence of ≈ 2.53 . It is worth noting in passing that by approximating $\sqrt{65}$ by 8, we recover Archimedes' approximation $\pi \approx \frac{22}{7}$, and by better approximating $\sqrt{65}$ by $8 + \frac{1}{16}$, we obtain the Chongzhi approximation $\pi \approx \frac{355}{113}$. It should be noted that both fractions $\frac{22}{7}$ and $\frac{355}{113}$ are convergents of the continued fraction of π .

This second construction is performed as follows:

Construct a right triangle ABC , right-angled at B , such that $AB = 8$ and $BC = 1$. Let D be the intersection point of the circle centered at C passing through B with the segment AC . The line passing through B and parallel to AC intersects the line passing through D and parallel to BC at a point E . The line AE intersects the line

BC at a point F . The line passing through D and parallel to AF intersects the line BC at a point G . Finally, let G' be the symmetric point of G with respect to F and G'' be the symmetric point of F with respect to G' . We then have:

$$CG'' = 3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1} \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. Applying the Pythagorean theorem to the right triangle ABC (right-angled at B), we have:

$$AC^2 = AB^2 + BC^2 = 8^2 + 1^2 = 65,$$

which yields $AC = \sqrt{65}$.

On the other hand, by the very definition of the point D , we have $CD = CB = 1$. From this, we deduce:

$$AD = AC - CD = \sqrt{65} - 1.$$

Furthermore, since the quadrilaterals $DEFG$ and $DEBC$ are parallelograms by construction, we have:

$$GF = DE = CB = 1.$$

Now, applying Thales's theorem (the intercept theorem) to the triangle CAF with the secant line DG (which is parallel to AF), we obtain:

$$\frac{CG}{GF} = \frac{CD}{DA}.$$

Therefore, substituting the known values, we get:

$$CG = GF \times \frac{CD}{DA} = 1 \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1}.$$

Finally, since $G'G'' = FG' = GF = 1$ (by the very definition of the points G' and G''), we conclude that:

$$\begin{aligned} CG'' &= GG'' + CG \\ &= 3GF + CG \\ &= 3 \times 1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1} \\ &= 3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{65} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Construction 3. This construction makes use of the quadratic approximation:

$$\pi \approx \sqrt{51} - 4, \tag{3}$$

which carries an error of $\approx 1.6 \times 10^{-4}$ and a measure of intelligence of ≈ 1.85 . The construction is described as follows:

Construct an isosceles triangle ABC with apex A , such that $AB = AC = 5$ and $BC = 7$. Let A' be the symmetric point of A with respect to the line BC . Furthermore, let B' be the point on the segment AA' such that $AB' = 4$. We then obtain:

$$A'B' = \sqrt{51} - 4 \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. Let O denote the intersection point of the lines BC and AA' . Since ABC is an isosceles triangle, its altitude dropped from the apex A is also the perpendicular bisector of the segment BC . Consequently, we have:

$$OC = \frac{1}{2}BC = \frac{7}{2}.$$

Applying the Pythagorean theorem to the right triangle AOC (right-angled at O), we obtain:

$$AO^2 = AC^2 - OC^2 = 5^2 - \left(\frac{7}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{51}{4}.$$

This implies $AO = \frac{\sqrt{51}}{2}$. By definition of the point A' , it follows that:

$$AA' = 2 \cdot AO = \sqrt{51}.$$

Finally,

$$A'B' = AA' - AB' = \sqrt{51} - 4,$$

as required. \square

Construction 4. We employ the biquadratic approximation:

$$\pi \approx 4(\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2}) - 1, \quad (4)$$

with an error of $\approx 4.8 \times 10^{-4}$ and a measure of intelligence of ≈ 2.26 . This approximation can be derived by approximating the value of the function $x \mapsto \frac{\arcsin x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}$ at $x = \frac{\pi}{24}$ via its second-order Taylor expansion at the origin. It can also be obtained by neglecting the integral $\int_0^{\pi/12} (1 - \cos t)^2 dt$. The construction proceeds as follows:

Begin with a square $ABCD$ of side length 8. Inside this square, locate the points E and F such that the triangles BCE and CDF are equilateral. Finally, place the point G on the segment EF such that $EG = 1$. We then have:

$$FG = 4(\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2}) - 1 \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. We equip the plane with an orthonormal coordinate system (C, \vec{i}, \vec{j}) , where $\vec{i} = \frac{1}{8}\overrightarrow{CB}$ and $\vec{j} = \frac{1}{8}\overrightarrow{CD}$ (as in the figure above). Since the triangles CBE and CDF are equilateral, we have $CE = CF = 8$, the angle $(\overrightarrow{CB}, \overrightarrow{CE}) \equiv \frac{\pi}{3} \pmod{2\pi}$, and:

$$(\overrightarrow{CB}, \overrightarrow{CF}) = (\overrightarrow{CB}, \overrightarrow{CD}) - (\overrightarrow{CF}, \overrightarrow{CD}) \equiv \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{3} \equiv \frac{\pi}{6} \pmod{2\pi}.$$

The coordinates of the points E and F in the chosen frame are therefore: $E(8 \cos \frac{\pi}{3}, 8 \sin \frac{\pi}{3})$ and $F(8 \cos \frac{\pi}{6}, 8 \sin \frac{\pi}{6})$, which simplifies to: $E(4, 4\sqrt{3})$ and $F(4\sqrt{3}, 4)$. It follows that the distance EF is:

$$EF = \sqrt{(4\sqrt{3} - 4)^2 + (4 - 4\sqrt{3})^2} = \sqrt{2(4\sqrt{3} - 4)^2} = 4(\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2}).$$

Ultimately,

$$FG = EF - EG = 4(\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2}) - 1,$$

which completes the proof. \square

Construction 5. This construction is due to Kochański [4] and utilizes the biquadratic approximation:

$$\pi \approx \sqrt{\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}}, \quad (5)$$

which exhibits an error of $\approx 5.9 \times 10^{-5}$ and a measure of intelligence of ≈ 1.65 . The simplicity of Kochański's geometric construction stems from the algebraic identities:

$$\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3} = \left(3 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right)^2 + 2^2, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} = \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right).$$

The specifics of this construction are as follows:

Fix a point O in the plane and draw the circle \mathcal{C}_1 centered at O with radius 1. Choose a point A on \mathcal{C}_1 and draw the circle \mathcal{C}_2 centered at A with radius 1. Let B be one of the intersection points of \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 . Draw the circle \mathcal{C}_3 centered at B with radius 1. Let C be the intersection point of \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_3 (distinct from A). Let Δ be the line passing through O and perpendicular to OA , and D be the intersection point of AC with Δ . Finally, define E on the ray $[DO)$ such that $DE = 3$, and let F be the symmetric point of O with respect to A . Then:

$$EF = \sqrt{\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}} \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. Since the circles \mathcal{C}_1 , \mathcal{C}_2 , and \mathcal{C}_3 all share the same radius $R = 1$, we have

$$OA = AB = OB = BC = OC = 1. \quad (\star)$$

On the one hand, (\star) shows that the triangle OAB is equilateral, implying that the angle \widehat{OAB} measures 60° . On the other hand, (\star) shows that the quadrilateral $OABC$ is a rhombus (since all its sides are equal to 1). A well-known property of the rhombus is that its diagonals bisect its interior angles. Therefore, the line AC bisects the angle \widehat{OAB} , which implies that:

$$\widehat{DAO} = \frac{1}{2}\widehat{OAB} = \frac{1}{2}60^\circ = 30^\circ.$$

Furthermore, since the triangle DOA is right-angled at O , we have

$$DO = OA \cdot \tan(\widehat{DAO}) = 1 \cdot \tan(30^\circ) = 1 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}.$$

Thus,

$$OE = DE - DO = 3 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}.$$

Finally, since F lies on the line OA and (Δ) is perpendicular to OA at O , the triangle OEF is right-angled at O . Applying the Pythagorean theorem to the triangle OEF yields:

$$EF^2 = OE^2 + OF^2 = OE^2 + (2OA)^2 = \left(3 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right)^2 + 2^2 = \frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}.$$

Taking the square root gives

$$EF = \sqrt{\frac{40}{3} - 2\sqrt{3}},$$

as required. □

Construction 6. We use the quadratic approximation:

$$\pi \approx \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}} - 3, \quad (6)$$

which has an error of $\approx 3.3 \times 10^{-5}$ and a measure of intelligence of ≈ 1.11 . Although this approximation may lack aesthetic appeal due to the “large” integer 1207, it gives rise to a surprisingly simple geometric construction.

Construct a right isosceles triangle ABC , right-angled at B , such that $AB = BC = 6$. Locate a point D in the plane satisfying $AD = 7$ and $CD = 8$. Let H be the orthogonal projection of point D onto the line AC . Finally, let E be the point on the segment DH such that $HE = 3$. We then obtain:

$$DE = \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}} - 3 \approx \pi.$$

Geometric illustration:

Proof. Applying the Pythagorean theorem to the right isosceles triangle ABC , we find $AC = AB\sqrt{2} = 6\sqrt{2}$. Next, applying the Law of Cosines (Al-Kashi's theorem) to the triangle ACD , we have:

$$CD^2 = AC^2 + AD^2 - 2 \cdot AC \cdot AD \cdot \cos(\widehat{CAD}).$$

This yields:

$$\cos(\widehat{CAD}) = \frac{AC^2 + AD^2 - CD^2}{2 \cdot AC \cdot AD} = \frac{(6\sqrt{2})^2 + 7^2 - 8^2}{2 \cdot 6\sqrt{2} \cdot 7} = \frac{19}{28\sqrt{2}}.$$

Consequently,

$$\sin(\widehat{CAD}) = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2(\widehat{CAD})} = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{19}{28\sqrt{2}}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{28} \sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}}.$$

It follows that:

$$DH = AD \cdot \sin(\widehat{CAD}) = 7 \times \frac{1}{28} \sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}} = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}}.$$

Finally, we have:

$$DE = DH - EH = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{1207}{2}} - 3,$$

as required. \square

3. FURTHER PERSPECTIVES

There exist other highly interesting approximations of π , all of which were already noted in [2]. Although these values are theoretically constructible using a straightedge and compass, simple and elegant geometric constructions for them have yet to be discovered. A few notable examples are presented below:

Approximation	Error	Measure of intelligence
$\pi \approx \frac{3}{5}(3 + \sqrt{5})$ (due to Ramanujan)	4.8×10^{-5}	2.04
$\pi \approx 3 + \frac{\sqrt{30} - 1}{10\sqrt{10}}$	10^{-5}	1.39
$\pi \approx \frac{17}{11} \left(\frac{4}{\sqrt{15}} + 1 \right)$	4.8×10^{-7}	1.68
$\pi \approx 1 + \sqrt{\frac{8}{5}\sqrt{2} - \sqrt{3} - 4\sqrt{5} + 13}$	2.6×10^{-8}	1.68

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